

1) Introduction

Social disparities in educational attainment have been researched for many years. Research has proposed two prominent theories explaining educational inequalities are rational choice theory (Boudon, 1974) and cultural reproduction theory (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1990). While the first approach explains educational inequalities as results of socially stratified decision-making throughout the educational career, the second approach views the cause of educational inequalities primarily parents' economic, social and cultural resources – of which cultural resources can be considered particularly important (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1990).

Since the intergenerational transmission of cultural capital is considered a key mechanism in cultural reproduction, the focus often lies on the cultural resources of parents. Bourdieu and Passeron (1990) argue that, due to less stimulating home learning environments, children from less privileged families perform worse at school. However, it has been proposed to distinguish between parental and individual cultural resources (Chin & Phillips, 2004). This raises the question whether individual cultural capital has a unique effect on educational outcomes – when separated from parental resources. Does individual cultural capital affect students' educational attainment – and if so, through which processes?

To find answers to this question, we use a broad operationalization of cultural capital. Besides established measurements like participation in highbrow cultural activities and non-formal arts education courses, we also extend previous research by investigating the

role of activities that are more accessible: arts education at schools, engaging in cultural clubs and arts education at youth centers. These activities have in common that they can be a means to accumulate cultural capital independently from one's parents. Through such a broad operationalization we aim to explore which specific activities can contribute to social mobility. Moreover, we analyze underlying mechanisms: To what extent can educational achievement (mathematics and reading) as well as decision-making (aspirations and academic track attendance) explain the relationship between individual cultural capital and educational attainment?

Overall, in this paper we investigate how students' individual cultural capital, affects educational attainment. We further explore whether different forms of arts education contribute to social mobility and examine underlying mechanisms. We will use Germany as an example of education systems with a high degree of social inequality. The upper secondary degree ("Abitur") determines German universities' choice of students to a great extent. Thus, the grades that one receives at school are generally crucial for university entry and mark an important level of educational attainment. Utilizing data from the German National Educational Panel Study we estimate Average Treatment Effects in linear probability models using entropy balancing (Hainmueller, 2012) to answer our research questions.

2) State of Research

The effect of cultural capital on educational achievement has been studied many times with grades or standardized test scores typically being the variable of interest (Andersen &

Hansen, 2011; Blaabæk, 2020; Gaddis, 2013; Jæger, 2011; Roscigno & Ainsworth-Darnell, 1999; Sikora et al., 2018; Wildhagen, 2009). In a meta-analysis, Jheng et al. (2023) find positive associations, which are largest for objectified, followed by institutionalized and embodied cultural capital. In another meta-analysis, C. Y. Tan et al. (2019) find that the effects are dependent on the specific operationalization of cultural capital. They review the effects of many different measures on achievement, finding that cultural participation is placed in the lower middle range of effect sizes among all variables under study. Thus, the variety of operationalizations of cultural capital is controversially discussed in the literature (Vryonides, 2007) and has been identified as problematic (Jæger, 2022). There also is literature on the effect of cultural capital on educational attainment (for an overview see Jæger, 2011). Researchers find positive effects on years of schooling (de Graaf et al., 2000; Kraaykamp & Notten, 2016) and completion of degrees (de Graaf & de Graaf, 2002; Evans et al., 2010).

With the literature being extensive on the importance of cultural capital for educational achievement, the question arises how this relates to educational attainment. One can assume educational achievement to be crucial for educational attainment. However, educational decision-making can play an equally important role (Boudon, 1974). Thus, when researching educational attainment, both should be taken into consideration.

Educational aspirations often precede such decisions so that they are commonly examined in research on educational transitions (see Schindler & Lörz, 2012, p. 648). In empirical research, it has been shown that educational aspirations are associated with parental cultural capital (G. L. C. Tan & Fang, 2023). However, aspirations have so far typically been

understood as a mediator between cultural capital and academic achievement, finding that aspirations mediate the relationship between the two (Raudenská, 2022; Wildhagen, 2009). Furthermore, research on cultural capital often (implicitly or explicitly) refers to the capital of parents (de Graaf et al., 2000; Kraaykamp & Notten, 2016). Measurements of parental social status are often part of the analytic models (Raudenská, 2022; Wildhagen, 2009). Parental social status is highly relevant for cultural capital research because social status and cultural capital are linked with each other and because, in addition to parental cultural capital, parental social status can be expected to foster cultural capital acquisition (Jæger & Breen, 2016). A distinction can be made between parental and child cultural capital (Chin & Phillips, 2004; Sullivan, 2001). However, researchers often do not clearly distinguish between the two. Instead, studies seem to depend on the variables that are present in the dataset used, often without considering the differences between parent and child variables (see Heppt et al., 2022). Some authors do distinguish between parental and child cultural capital (Georg, 2004; Kisida et al., 2014). But the role of children in cultural (re-)production processes still is considered a research gap (Jæger, 2022, p. 126).

Previous research also suggests that effects of cultural capital on academic success can vary between children from different socioeconomic backgrounds. The reproduction model (Bourdieu & Passeron, 1990) assumes that students from privileged families have higher returns to cultural capital, whereas the mobility model (DiMaggio, 1982) proposes that students from disadvantaged families benefit more. Evidence has been found for both (Aschaffenburg & Maas, 1997; de Graaf et al., 2000; Hu et al., 2022; Jæger, 2011) so that Blaskó (2003, p. 5) concludes that “cultural assets have both helped the upper classes to

maintain their existing positions but they have also provided a possible source for those occupying lower positions in the social hierarchy to support their children getting forward”.

In sum, empirical research investigating the associations between cultural capital and educational success so far has been limited in three ways. First, studies often do not clearly separate the effects of parental and child cultural capital. From the perspective of social mobility, it appears promising to investigate how students’ individual cultural capital affects educational attainment. Second, to our knowledge aspirations have been investigated only as a mediator between cultural capital and school achievement so far (Dumais, 2002; Raudenská, 2022; Wildhagen, 2009). Since there still is little research on the mechanisms that translate cultural capital into educational success (Kingston, 2001; Raudenská, 2022), it appears promising to analyze both achievement and decision-making variables as mediators between cultural capital and educational attainment. Third, contradictory results have been found regarding the differentials in the effects of cultural capital by low and high status backgrounds, providing evidence for both the assumptions of the mobility and the reproduction model. This calls for providing additional evidence.

3) Theory

Cultural Capital and its Operationalization

Bourdieu (1986) distinguishes three forms of cultural capital: the embodied (tastes, behavior), institutionalized (educational certificates) and objectified (cultural possessions) state. Cultural capital is commonly operationalized using participation in highbrow culture, which Aschaffenburg and Maas (1997, p. 577) have called “the best proxy for cultural

capital". However, measuring cultural capital remains complex and has received much scholarly attention (Sullivan, 2007; Vryonides, 2007). The fundamental issue lies in the persistent lack of conceptual clarity in Bourdieu's writings, which has led to a "mushrooming of alternative interpretations of what cultural capital is" (Jæger, 2022, p. 122). Consequently, there is no consensus on a definition of cultural capital – it is variously understood as cultural taste, values, behavior or even competence (Dumais, 2015).

Including masscultural activities in analyses on cultural capital allows for a better representation of actual arts education practices in three regards. First, it allows for including sociocultural practices, which have long been an integral part of arts education (Rosenblum, 1981). Including them has implications for social stratification ("omnivore thesis," see Peterson, 1992), but they are rarely used as indicators of cultural capital in empirical research. Second, the perspective considers that arts education infrastructure differs greatly between urban and rural areas (Fobel, 2022), which means in different regions different cultural practices may serve as cultural capital, with implications for social mobility research (Connor et al., 2023). Third, it considers that arts education practices are not only limited to non-formal activities but also include formal and informal learning (Kraehe et al., 2016). Thus, it seems worth investigating to what extent diverse dimensions of arts education can function as cultural capital within the education system.

At the same time, we expect non-formal highbrow activities to have more substantial effects on educational attainment, since their goals and settings are more aligned with schooling: students process cognitively demanding tasks in controlled environments where they need to concentrate. Thus, such activities are more focused on learning. Additionally, teachers might perceive this as productive leisure time, reinforcing positive effects through signals of

academic brilliance. In contrast, informal and formal activities might have weaker effects on educational attainment. Informal, lowbrow activities are often less education-oriented and more about free expression, creativity, and socializing. Formal cultural activities, on the other hand, lack the potential to distinguish oneself from others as well as the potential to create a larger social network.

Cultural Capital and Inequality in Educational Attainment

Two models have been established for many years when analyzing the effect of cultural capital on educational attainment: the reproduction model (Bourdieu, 1986; Bourdieu & Passeron, 1990) and the mobility model (DiMaggio, 1982). The reproduction model proposes that the social hierarchies are perpetuated across generations through the transmission of cultural capital from parents to children. The children's cultural capital is assumed to be advantageous within the education system (Jæger & Breen, 2016).

Consequently, children from more privileged families will attain higher educational qualifications as well as occupational status and that later the same process will repeat with the following generation.

The mobility model proposes that cultural capital allows for social mobility. It assumes that cultural capital can be acquired outside one's family of origin and that it is especially advantageous for students from disadvantaged backgrounds. Thus, the model proposes that cultural capital allows for those students to catch up in the education system. In sum, the reproduction model emphasizes intergenerational transmission and persistence of inequalities, while the mobility model focuses on the potential of cultural capital for social

upward movement (Aschaffenburg & Maas, 1997; Hu et al., 2022; Jæger, 2022; Nagel et al., 2010).

Cultural Capital, Achievement and Decision-Making

Besides theory on cultural reproduction processes, rational choice theory has also been productive for the investigation of educational stratification, particularly the distinction between primary and secondary effects (Boudon, 1974). Primary effects refer to “the association between children’s class backgrounds and their actual levels of academic performance” (Jackson et al., 2007, p. 212); i.e., it is assumed that students from privileged families have more advantageous conditions for achieving better academic performance than students from less privileged families. The debate on how exactly this primary effect manifests through cultural capital is ongoing. A distinction is made between biasing teachers’ perceptions and direct effects on achievement. The former is assumed to take place via signaling academic brilliance and thus receiving more support by teachers. In line with the latter, it is argued that cultural capital fosters a set of non-cognitive skills that, in turn, enhance educational achievement (Breinholt & Jæger, 2020; Jæger, 2022; Mikus et al., 2019).

In contrast, secondary effects refer to differences in educational decision-making that are due to the children’s social background even when keeping constant their academic performance. These choices can lead to different educational transitions and are typically preceded by aspirations (see Schindler & Lörz, 2012, p. 648). According to the Wisconsin model (Sewell et al., 1969) students’ social environment can shape their educational aspirations. Since cultural practices have typical social settings, one can expect them to

have an impact on students' educational aspirations via socialization processes with significant others (Eccles & Wigfield, 2020; Potts, 2015). In tracked education systems like in Germany, educational decision-making affects track attendance. Like with aspirations, cultural activities can generate social norms in the students that can lead to an increased perceived importance of attending the academic track. Given the nature of the academic track to prepare the students for higher qualifications, this can in turn affect the students' educational attainment. In sum, both educational achievement and decision-making can be expected to mediate the relationship between cultural capital and educational attainment.

4) The Present Study

This study pursues three goals. First, we propose to make a clear distinction between parental and student cultural capital. Our goal is to investigate whether students' cultural participation affects attaining the upper secondary degree when controlling for confounders such as parental socioeconomic status and cultural capital. We suggest that formal and informal as well as sociocultural arts education participation can function as cultural capital. Thus, we hypothesize that both highbrow and lowbrow cultural participation has a positive effect on educational attainment (hypothesis 1).

Second, we further analyze the mechanisms how cultural capital affects educational outcomes. Prior findings suggest that primary effects are at work, i.e., achievement mediates the relationship between cultural participation and attaining the upper secondary degree (hypothesis 2). Also, we assume that secondary effects can explain the association

and thus hypothesize that aspirations and attending the academic track mediate the relationship between cultural participation and educational attainment (hypothesis 3).

Third, we aim to evaluate further assumptions of the reproduction and the mobility model. Both expect the effects of cultural capital on educational attainment to vary between students from disadvantaged and privileged backgrounds. The reproduction model proposes a “Matthew effect”, meaning students from privileged families benefit more from cultural capital in the education system. The mobility model assumes the opposite, i.e., that students from disadvantaged backgrounds have higher returns to cultural capital and thus can catch up in the education system. While the two hypotheses are often considered to be contrary, they can be combined, assuming that students from both disadvantaged and privileged socioeconomic backgrounds benefit more from cultural capital than students from families of average status (hypothesis 4).

Due to a lack of previous findings, some of our assumptions can only be investigated in an exploratory way by following more general research questions rather than concrete hypotheses: How do the effects of specific operationalizations of cultural participation compare to each other? To what extent do achievement and decision-making mediate the relationship between cultural participation and educational attainment? Which of them mediates a larger share of the effect? Thus, we will conduct both hypothesis-driven and exploratory analyses.

We have summarized our assumptions about causal mechanisms in a Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG, see Figure 1). Our effects of interest are from cultural activities on educational attainment as well as the mediating paths through educational achievement and decision-

making. Obvious confounders to these relationships are social origin (parental income, occupation, education, cultural capital) as well as the individuals' gender and immigration status. With other variables, the causal relationships are rather ambiguous. In line with the existing literature, we consider it highly likely that cultural activities affect competencies (see Raudenská, 2022). However, reverse causation cannot be ruled out, which means that competencies could confound the relationship between cultural activities and educational attainment. The same applies to educational decisions: Aspirations and school track could cause students to attend cultural activities and attain higher educational degrees and thus be confounders. We consider it highly likely that there is reverse causation between the mediators as well, while the effect of competencies on educational decisions appears more dominant to us than vice versa. All these ambiguous causal relationships complicate the identification of causal effects and will be addressed in robustness checks.

Figure 1: Directed Acyclic Graph

5) Data and Methods

To examine the above-mentioned effects of student cultural participation on attaining the upper secondary degree, we perform secondary analyses using data from starting cohort 3 (SC3) of the German National Educational Panel Study, dataset version 13.0.0 (NEPS, 2024). In NEPS, a broad variety of psychological and sociological constructs is measured (see Blossfeld & Roßbach, 2019) so that these datasets are amongst the most comprehensive on education in Germany. The sample was drawn from German schools starting in 2010/11 (grade 5/wave 1). All secondary school types including special needs schools are included. In total, over 8,000 students have participated in data collection along with their parents, teachers, and school principals. Data collection is still ongoing using individual tracking since the target persons have left the secondary school system by now.

Through their longitudinal design, the data allow for analyzing the effects of cultural participation on later attainment of the upper secondary degree. For variables with data available at multiple waves we chose one time-point for each variable (Figure 2). For a few constructs, data on mediator variables were collected after data on independent variables. We utilized all available cases from all types of schools, which resulted in a sample of 8,317 students. We used data from wave 1 (average age: 11 years) through wave 12 (average age: 22 years).

Figure 2: Overview of time-points used for measurement

	Grade	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13/individual tracking			
	Wave	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12
	Year	10/11	11/12	12/13	13/14	14/15	15	15/16	16/17	17/18	18/19	19/20	20/21
Abitur												AN	AN
Highbrow activities						AN							
Courses outside school				AN	AN	AN							
Arts profile		AN				AN							
Culture club							AN		IM				
Arts at youth center							AN						
Mathematics achievement		RC				AN							
Reading achievement		RC					AN						
Aspiration		RC	IM	IM	IM	AN							
Academic track school		RC	RC			AN	AN						
Male		AN	AN	AN	AN	AN	AN	AN	AN	AN			
Immigrant background		AN	AN	AN									
Parental HISEI		AN	IM	IM	IM			IM					
Parental highbrow activities		AN						IM					
Parental cultural possessions							AN						

Note: AN = used in analysis, RC = used in robustness checks, IM = used as auxiliary variable during imputation. Time points used in analysis are additionally marked with a grey background for better visibility.

Measures

Outcome. To determine whether an individual has obtained the *upper secondary degree* (“Abitur”), we use a variable generated by the NEPS research data center that integrates information from various sources regarding the attainment of educational qualifications. The academic track is usually completed after 12 or 13 grades in Germany, depending on the federal state. Thus, we needed information from after regular completion of grade 13 (= waves 11 or 12) to gain a valid operationalization. The data stem from episode data, which offers positive information indicating the acquisition of a qualification but lacks information on the absence of said qualification. To create a valid measurement, we established a binary

variable through a three-step process: [1] If there is available information confirming that the target person has acquired the upper secondary degree, we utilize these data as-is. [2] In cases where the data do not explicitly confirm the individual's attainment of the upper secondary degree, but they have participated in either wave 11 or wave 12 of the study, we deduce that the absence of information is indicative of the individual not having obtained the degree. [3] For individuals lacking data on the acquisition of the upper secondary degree and not having participated in either wave 11 or wave 12, we consider it highly likely that the information is missing and therefore assign a missing value. By employing this method, we aim to provide a robust assessment of educational attainment within our dataset.

Exposure. Students' *highbrow activities* were operationalized using three items ("How many times have you done the following things in the last 12 months? a) visited a museum or an art exhibition, b) visited an opera, ballet or classic concert, c) been to the theater"), that were measured from 1 ("never") to 5 ("more than 5 times"). We created a variable indicating whether students attended at least one of these activities. To assess formal arts education, we used information on the presence of an *arts profile* at the school provided by the school principals ("Does your school have a special profile? If so, which one? – Artistic subjects"). This information was subsequently attributed to students enrolled in those respective schools. We measured arts education *courses outside school* using data derived from verbatim responses (Burkhard & Lampel, 2023). These data capture whether a student had engaged in various artistic disciplines. The categories considered as part of arts education encompass music, dance, theater, visual arts, literature, photography, media design, circus arts, as well as the category "other/arts education". Subsequently, we

constructed a variable to indicate whether the student had participated in at least one course within these artistic domains. Measurement of involvement in *cultural clubs* was determined through a binary response recorded in the student questionnaire (“Do you participate in a culture club such as a theater group, youth orchestra, club cultivating local history, folklore club, etc.”). Similar to cultural clubs, engagement in *arts activities at youth centers* was assessed in the questionnaire (“Which activities do you use at the youth center? making music, dancing, acting or other artistic activities”). All treatment variables are binary.

Mediators. To investigate the role of primary effects (hypothesis 2), we measure individuals’ *academic achievement* with standardized test scores of their math and reading competence (see Fuß et al., 2021), which were provided as WLE-estimates. To analyze secondary effects (hypothesis 3), we dichotomized students’ *idealistic educational aspirations* (“Regardless of which school you attend and how good your grades are, what kind of school-leaving qualification would you like to obtain?”) so that the variable represents whether they would like to obtain the upper secondary degree or not. To measure attendance of the *academic school type*, we created a binary variable indicating whether a student attended the “Gymnasium”. All mediators were z-standardized to make their interpretation comparable.

Parental covariates. Parents’ *income* was operationalized as the monthly household income, resulting in a continuous response, which we z-standardized. We employed data on *parental occupation* as measured by the International Socio-Economic Index of Occupational Status (ISEI-08, Ganzeboom, 2010). Subsequently, we computed the highest ISEI score among both parents for utilization in our analytical procedures (see FDZ-LIfBi, 2023). Similarly, we used the dominance approach to measure the highest *parental*

education. It was provided on the CASMIN scale ranging from 0 (“no qualification”) to 8 (“university degree”). To measure *parental embodied cultural capital*, we employed the identical scale utilized for measuring highbrow activities among students (see above). We assessed the scale’s reliability using McDonald’s omega ($\omega = .70$) and then used its mean in our analyses. *Parental objectified cultural capital* was measured using information on three cultural goods (“At home, do you have ... a) classic literature (e.g. by Goethe)? b) books with poems? c) works of art (e.g. paintings)?”). We created a binary variable for our analyses that indicates whether at least one of the three cultural goods is present at home.

Individual covariates. We used information on students’ *gender* provided at multiple time-points. To harmonize the available information, we calculated the mode across all available waves. The variable takes on the value of 1 for males and 0 for females (nonbinary gender was not assessed). We established a binary variable to indicate the presence of *immigrant status* among students. Immigrant status was deemed to be present if either the students themselves or at least one of their parents were born outside Germany.

Estimation Strategy

To estimate the effects of student cultural participation on attaining the upper secondary school diploma, we use entropy balancing (Hainmueller, 2012) to balance covariates.

Entropy balancing is similar to other weighting/matching methods in the sense that an observational dataset is preprocessed so that the biased selection into exposure is corrected, creating a quasi-experimental design. Specifically, entropy balancing generates weights that will adjust a set of covariates between the “treated” and “untreated”. These weights can then be used just like sampling weights to strengthen identification of causal

effects in further analyses. Separately for each model, we create weights to balance the following covariates: parental income, occupation, education, cultural activities, and cultural possessions as well as the students' gender and immigrant background. After balancing, we assess whether covariate balance was achieved.

Then, we first estimate the Average Treatment Effect (ATE) of each student cultural activity on attaining the upper secondary degree in a linear probability model without mediators. Second, to analyze the underlying mechanisms, we include mediator variables in a step-wise manner: we add reading and mathematics achievement as mediators (primary effect then include aspirations and academic track as a mediators while controlling for the achievement variables (secondary effect), and lastly use all mediators simultaneously in our analyses, while assessing the percent mediated of each model. Third, we investigate effect heterogeneity by ISEI quartiles. To do so, we repeat the analysis conducted previously but now differentiate between ISEI quartiles.

Additionally, we conduct robustness checks to examine whether the effects are sensitive to balancing additional covariates. To this end, we estimate the effects for those variables with a significant ATE using various sets of covariates during entropy balancing. Our models already contain the basic set of parental and individual covariates as described above. Then, we utilize the nature of our panel dataset and include measures of educational achievement (reading and mathematics) and decision-making (aspirations and school track) from previous waves as covariates. We first add measures of reading and mathematics achievement from wave 1 (grade 5) as covariates. Second, we remove the achievement variables but add measures of educational aspirations and academic track attendance from wave 1 (grade 5). Third, we include all four previous measures. Using the information from

previous time points allows us to estimate the ATEs and mediation effects under the condition that they are only identified when considering potential reverse causation from the mediators.

Data processing and descriptive analyses are conducted within the R statistical environment (R Core Team, 2021). We impute missing data $m = 10$ times using the mice package (van Buuren & Groothuis-Oudshoorn, 2011; van Buuren 2018) with multilevel predictive mean matching (“2l.pmm”) from the miceadds package (Robitzsch & Grund, 2025). For entropy balancing, we use the packages MatchThem (Pishgar et al., 2021) and cobalt (Greifer, 2025) to assess covariate balance. Packages survey (Lumley, 2024) and lavaan (Rosseel et al., 2025) are then used to estimate the effects. The Scientific Use Files containing the data are available to scholars and the complete set of scripts required to replicate the analyses are available for download¹. Given access to the Remote NEPS environment, all statistical procedures presented in this article can be reproduced.

6) Results

Descriptives

We descriptively examined the data with summary statistics (Table A1), finding that around three quarter of the students do attain the upper secondary degree – before imputation of missing values. Most students attended at least one highbrow cultural activity (81% of all students) followed by courses outside school (39% of all students), attending a school with

¹ <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18748906>

an arts profile (21%), participation in a culture club (13%) and arts activities at youth centers (7%).

Turning to bivariate correlations (Figure 3), we find that students' highbrow activities (.21) and courses outside school (.18) are substantially associated with attaining the upper secondary degree. Correlations between degree attainment and participation in cultural clubs (.08), attending a school with an arts profile (.04) and arts activities at youth centers (-.01) are lower. The different forms of student cultural participation are overall rather weakly correlated with each other. The mediator variables (.34-.59) along with parental (.19-.30) and school (.15-.45) control variables are positively correlated with obtaining the upper secondary degree. Individual control variables, however, show zero or negative correlations with most other variables including educational attainment.

Figure 3: Correlation matrix of all variables used (Pearson correlations)

Before analyzing treatment effects, we assessed whether covariate balance was achieved during entropy balancing. In total, we generated weights 20 times. For each of the five treatment variables (i.e., cultural activities), four sets of covariates were balanced: [1] “Basic”: parental income, parental occupation, parental education, parental highbrow activities, parental cultural possessions, students’ gender, immigrant background. [2]

“Achievement”: Basic + mathematics and reading competencies from grade 5 (wave 1). [3]
“Decisions”: Basic + aspirations and academic track from grade 5 (wave 1). [4] “All”: Basic + Achievement + Decisions. Instead of reporting the balance of each weighting procedure, we provide a summary here using standardized mean differences (SMD) and Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistics (KSS). Both quantify differences between the treated and control group for each variable after balancing. The closer both measures are to 0, the better the balance. There have been attempts to define thresholds ranging from .05 to .25 (see Greifer, 2025). However, there does not yet seem to be a consensus about cut-off values. Our results (see Figure A1 in the appendix) show that all SMDs are close to 0 (11th decimal place). KSS is mostly below 0.05 and exceeds 0.15 in very few cases. This means that the differences in covariates have successfully been eliminated, while the differences in cultural participation remains. These differences can now be exploited to estimate the effects of cultural participation on educational attainment.

Step 1: Average Treatment Effects

In the first step of our analysis, we estimated Average Treatment Effects of all five cultural participation variables on educational attainment using the basic set of covariates as described above (hypothesis 1). Results from linear probability models (Figure 4, also see Table A2 in the appendix) show that the probability of attaining the upper secondary degree increases by attending highbrow activities (11.4%) and courses outside school (9.3%). Results for attending a school with an arts profile (1.7%), participation in culture clubs (5.0%), and arts activities at youth centers (-3.2%) are non-significant at the 5%-level. We conclude that, depending on the specific activity, child cultural participation can affect

Figure 4: Average Treatment Effects of Student Cultural Activities on Educational Attainment

Note: Balanced covariates were parental income, parental occupation, parental education, parental highbrow activities, parental cultural possessions as well as students' gender and immigrant background, N = 8,317. Missing values were imputed m = 10 times.

Figure 5: Mediation effects with 95% confidence intervals

Note: Balanced covariates were parental income, parental occupation, parental education, parental highbrow activities, parental cultural possessions as well as students' gender and immigrant background. Confidence intervals were obtained using R = 1,500 bootstraps. N = 8,317. Missing values were imputed m = 10 times.

attaining the upper secondary degree when controlling for socioeconomic status, parental cultural capital as well as gender and immigrant background.

Step 2: Including mediators step-wise

Turning to mediation effects, we find that both achievement and educational decisions mediate the effects (hypotheses 2 and 3). In the following description of our results (Figure 5, also see Table A3 in the appendix), we will refer merely to the mediation of variables that had a significant ATE before. For both highbrow activities and courses outside school, the indirect effect increases through the three steps of including [1] achievement variables, [2] educational decision variables while controlling for achievement and [3] both achievement and decision variables as mediators. For highbrow activities, the percent mediated increases from 42.6% (achievement) over 65.3% (decisions) to 70.4 % (all). For courses outside school, the percents mediated are 50.5%, 76.9% and 80.7% respectively. We conclude that secondary effects are stronger than primary effects for both variables.

Step 3: Effect heterogeneity by ISEI quartiles

To test the combined assumptions from the reproduction and mobility models whether students from privileged and disadvantaged backgrounds benefit more from cultural capital within the education system than students from average status families (hypothesis 4), we repeat the analysis presented in step 1, but now differentiate the effects by ISEI quartiles (Figure 6, also see Table A2 in the appendix). None of the resulting patterns supports our hypothesis. In some cases, point estimates are lower in the first and fourth quartile (highbrow activities), while in others they tend to be higher for students from privileged backgrounds (arts at youth centers) or similar for each quartile (arts profile, courses

outside school, culture club). Overall, the differences are small and the confidence intervals largely overlap, which indicates that there are no significant differences between the different family backgrounds. We find no evidence neither for students from privileged nor from disadvantaged families having higher returns to cultural capital in the education system.

Figure 6: Effect heterogeneity by ISEI quartiles (from 1 = lowest to 4 = highest) with 95% confidence intervals

Note: Balanced covariates were parental income, parental occupation, parental education, parental highbrow activities, parental cultural possessions as well as students' gender and immigrant background, N = 8,317. Missing values were imputed m = 10 times.

7) Robustness Checks

We conducted robustness checks to examine the effects under different causal assumptions. For all previously reported results, we only used parental and individual covariates. Now, we reanalyzed the data using three additional sets of covariates (Figure A2 and Table A2 in the appendix). Our results show that the effects of highbrow activities and courses outside

school are robust to the inclusion of prior achievement (mathematics, reading) as well as prior educational decisions (aspirations, academic track). As can be expected, the estimates are smaller when including more covariates but remain statistically significant. For the other variables, we found similar patterns but under each covariate condition the effects remain nonsignificant.

We also checked the robustness of our mediation models (Figure A3 and Table A3 in the appendix). We found that the direct effects remain largely similar with some of them becoming nonsignificant through the inclusion of more covariates. In contrast, the total indirect effects and, in consequence, the total effects notably decrease. The results from our mediation models are overall robust to including prior achievement and educational decisions covariates.

8) Discussion

In this study, we examined whether students' cultural activities affect their attainment of upper secondary degrees by balancing various sets of parental and individual covariates. To analyze underlying mechanisms, we combined the considerations of Bourdieu and Passeron's (1990) cultural reproduction theory, DiMaggio's (1982) mobility model, and Boudon's (1974) distinction between primary and secondary effects. Using a large-scale panel dataset from Germany, we show that students' highbrow cultural activities as well as attending arts education courses outside school have an effect on educational attainment even when balancing socioeconomic status, parental cultural capital as well as gender and

immigrant background. Both achievement (mathematics and reading) and educational decisions (aspirations, track choice) mediate the effects.

First, our results show that students have agency of attaining upper secondary degrees through cultural participation, depending on the specific cultural activity. Irrespective of the socioeconomic and cultural conditions in the parental home as well as gender and immigrant background, cultural activities can have an effect on the acquisition of an upper secondary degree. Child cultural activities can increase the probability of attaining the *Abitur* by 11.4 (highbrow activities) and 9.3 (courses outside school) percentage points. This does not seem very large at first but is remarkable given the control of parental resources and individual-level covariates through entropy balancing. For these two variables, hypothesis 1 is supported.

Although participation in culture clubs and the choice of a school with an arts profile are socially stratified (Bons et al., 2022; Burkhard et al., 2024), these do not have a significant effect on educational attainment. The same applies to cultural activities at youth centers. Our results indicate that such “middle/lowbrow” cultural practices (see Jæger, 2022) are not as effective in fostering educational success as the highbrow ones. However, it is quite possible that the effects differ according to regional conditions (e.g. in rural areas), since cultural infrastructure varies greatly between urban and rural areas (Fobel, 2022).

Our findings suggest that prestigious leisure time activities have a larger impact on educational success than cultural practices in the formal education system or sociocultural sector. This is in line with previous research (Aschaffenburg & Maas, 1997) and might be due to the same reasons that “concerted cultivation” (Lareau, 2003) is considered effective

– leisure time activities can hold more potential for distinction than formal ones.

Sociocultural activities, on the other hand, are likely to be less oriented towards building distinctive attitudes and performing well academically, which would explain why they are less relevant for educational attainment. Accordingly, our results support the operationalization of cultural capital by highbrow leisure time cultural activities in the field of inequality research rather than formal and sociocultural practices (Aschaffenburg & Maas, 1997; Breinholt & Jæger, 2020; Georg, 2016; Yaish & Katz-Gerro, 2010). However, our study shows that the operationalization issues had thus far mostly been discussed for parental cultural capital. When assessing children’s cultural capital, several questions emerge: At what age do individuals grasp the distinction between lowbrow and highbrow cultural activities, and what implications does this hold for operationalizing child capital? How should institutionalized and objectified capital of children be measured? Does it generally depend on the life course which cultural practices function as cultural capital in society? Further exploring these questions remains a desideratum for future research.

Second, our results provide insights into the underlying mechanisms. Primary and secondary effects both mediate the relationship between cultural activities and educational attainment, with secondary effects outweighing the primary ones (support of hypotheses 2 and 3) – notably even though our understanding of secondary effects was conservative in the sense that only the mediation via aspirations and school track was considered a secondary effect. In other studies, secondary effects are sometimes not even modeled explicitly but are simply understood as the share of the effect that cannot be explained by achievement (see Jackson et al., 2007, p. 212; Scharf et al., 2020, p. 1259). To advance the understanding of the mechanisms through which cultural capital is translated into

educational success, future research should investigate the role of further variables like social capital and occupational interests.

Third, we find no evidence of differential effects of cultural activities by social background (“effect heterogeneity”). We expected that the effects of cultural activities on educational success would differ between social groups. However, we find no empirical evidence for this assumption. Hypothesis 4 must therefore be rejected. Still, heterogeneity might be found in more heterogeneous samples or for more extreme percentiles.

Last, we assessed whether our findings are robust to including additional covariates. Given that our mediators could potentially cause cultural activities in reverse, we used measurements of educational achievement and decisions from previous waves during balancing. We found that all reported effects are robust in this regard with the effects remaining significant. Since “family background stands out” (Jheng et al., 2023, p. 1) as a predictor of educational success as well as cultural participation, we were able to control for the most important confounders. However, it is hardly possible to exclude omitted variable bias with absolute certainty. For example, peers can be expected to influence both individuals’ cultural participation as well as their educational success. Since information on both peers is not available in our data, there is unmeasured confounding in our analyses. Thus, while we are confident that we considered the most important confounders, we must acknowledge that the effects are not fully identified.

Limitations in our study arise for several reasons. Causal conclusions are further limited by the fact that in some cases the mediator variables were collected after the treatment variable (see Figure 2). However, this only applies to treatment variables (i.e., cultural

activities) that had nonsignificant effects. Furthermore, although highbrow activities and courses outside school hold promise for fostering social mobility, participation in these activities remains disproportionately skewed toward students from privileged backgrounds. For these activities to effectively contribute to social mobility, it is essential that disadvantaged students gain access to them. In addition, cultural capital and in particular secondary effects could be operationalized more comprehensively, which is being debated in the literature (Jæger, 2022). For example, it has been proposed to put more emphasis on the digitization of cultural capital (Calderón Gómez, 2020). However, our operationalization options were limited, given that we conducted secondary analysis of already existing data. Future research will also need to work theoretically on the concept of child cultural capital and its impact on educational success. The present study provides initial starting points for such a conceptualization. In addition, it would be worth investigating how the role of cultural activities changes over time – as education expands, are cultural resources becoming an increasingly distinguishing feature? Finally, the question arises whether our findings only appear in highly stratified education systems such as our example of Germany or whether these patterns of inequality are robust internationally.

Overall, this article provides deeper insights into the effects of adolescents' cultural activities on educational success, going beyond the current state of research. Previous research has often focused on the cultural resources of the parental home, has not examined the underlying processes in detail and conclusions regarding causality were limited. This article provides more precise insights into how children's cultural activities affect the attainment of upper secondary degrees, and which processes explain these

relationships – besides the socioeconomic and cultural conditions in the family. For research on social stratification, the findings of this article will help future research to better understand the precise ways in which cultural resources contribute to social mobility.

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9) Appendix

Table A1: Summary statistics

Variable	Min	Max	Mean	SD	Skewness	Kurtosis	n valid values
Abitur	0	1	0.78	0.41	-1.34	-0.19	3810
Highbrow activities	0	1	0.81	0.39	-1.58	0.48	5590
Arts profile	0	1	0.21	0.41	1.40	-0.05	6324
Courses outside school	0	1	0.39	0.49	0.47	-1.78	7018
Culture club	0	1	0.13	0.34	2.20	2.83	5122
Arts at youth center	0	1	0.07	0.25	3.39	9.52	5419
Mathematics achievement	-3.49	4.40	0.00	1.00	0.28	0.07	4888
Reading achievement	-2.93	4.36	0.00	1.00	0.26	0.19	4578
Aspiration	-1.29	0.77	0.00	1.00	-0.52	-1.73	5495
Academic track	-0.93	1.07	0.00	1.00	0.14	-1.98	5309
Gender (male)	0	1	0.52	0.50	-0.08	-1.99	8313
Immigrant background	0	1	0.26	0.44	1.12	-0.75	8083
Parental Income	-1.02	29.92	0.00	1.00	14.68	649.93	3535
Parental Occupation	-2.06	1.68	0.00	1.00	-0.17	-1.10	5528
Parental Education	0.00	8.00	5.10	2.11	-0.13	-0.95	5613
Parental highbrow activities	1	5	2.01	0.88	0.95	0.561	4154
Parental cultural possessions	0	1	0.62	0.32	-0.35	-0.95	3249

Table A2: Average Treatment Effects for multiple sets of covariates and quartile analyses with standard errors

Treatment	Full Sample	Quartiles			
		1	2	3	4
<i>Covariates</i>					
Highbrow Activities					
<i>Basic</i>	.114 * (.018)	.058 (.039)	.109 * (.042)	.156 * (.050)	.101 * (.049)
<i>Achievement</i>	.080 * (.018)	–	–	–	–
<i>Decisions</i>	.062 * (.018)	–	–	–	–
<i>All</i>	.054 * (.018)	–	–	–	–
Arts Profile					
<i>Basic</i>	.017 (.018)	.007 (.047)	-.001 (.038)	.039 (.034)	-.014 (.029)
<i>Achievement</i>	.002 (.018)	–	–	–	–
<i>Decisions</i>	-.011 (.019)	–	–	–	–
<i>All</i>	-.013 (.020)	–	–	–	–
Courses Out. School					
<i>Basic</i>	.093 * (.019)	.094 (.052)	.069 (.035)	.071 (.037)	.071 * (.025)
<i>Achievement</i>	.059 * (.019)	–	–	–	–
<i>Decisions</i>	.052 * (.018)	–	–	–	–
<i>All</i>	.041 * (.018)	–	–	–	–
Culture Club					
<i>Basic</i>	.050 (.026)	.073 (.075)	.036 (.052)	.043 (.041)	.030 (.027)
<i>Achievement</i>	.035 (.025)	–	–	–	–
<i>Decisions</i>	.038 (.026)	–	–	–	–
<i>All</i>	.033 (.026)	–	–	–	–
Arts at Youth Center					
<i>Basic</i>	-.032 (.032)	-.066 (.072)	-.049 (.084)	.021 (.057)	-.036 (.063)
<i>Achievement</i>	-.014 (.031)	–	–	–	–
<i>Decisions</i>	-.035 (.029)	–	–	–	–
<i>All</i>	-.025 (.030)	–	–	–	–

Note: The quartile results were obtained by subsetting the dataset for each quartile. N = 8,317. Missing values were imputed m = 10 times. The four covariate sets included the following variables. [1] “Basic”: parental income, parental occupation, parental education, parental highbrow activities, parental cultural possessions, students’ gender, immigrant background. [2] “Achievement”: Basic + mathematics and reading competencies from grade 5 (wave 1). [3] “Decisions”: Basic + aspirations and academic track from grade 5 (wave 1). [4] “All”: Basic + Achievement + Decisions.

Table A3: Direct, indirect, and total effects with 95% confidence intervals and % mediated for multiple combinations of covariates and mediators

Treatment	Achievement Mediators				Decision Mediators				All Mediators			
	Direct	Indirect	Total	% mediated	Direct	Indirect	Total	% mediated	Direct	Indirect	Total	% mediated
<i>Covariates</i>												
Highbrow Activities												
<i>Basic</i>	.066 * [.035; .103]	.049 * [.035; .065]	.115 * [.087; .144]	42.6	.034 * [.008; .070]	.064 * [.048; .081]	.098 * [.071; .130]	65.3	.034 * [.008; .071]	.081 * [.061; .100]	.115 * [.087; .144]	70.4
<i>Achievement</i>	.054 * [.026; .091]	.027 * [.011; .040]	.080 * [.052; .144]	33.8	.030 * [.003; .067]	.041 * [.025; .058]	.071 * [.045; .104]	57.8	.030 * [.003; .066]	.049 * [.031; .069]	.080 * [.052; .111]	61.3
<i>Decisions</i>	.033 * [.003; .069]	.029 * [.015; .043]	.062 * [.034; .092]	46.8	.031 * [.007; .065]	.021 * [.007; .036]	.053 * [.026; .083]	39.6	.032 * [.006; .065]	.031 * [.014; .047]	.062 * [.034; .092]	50.0
<i>All</i>	.035 * [.006; .073]	.020 * [.005; .034]	.054 * [.028; .084]	37.0	.030 * [.005; .063]	.018 * [.003; .033]	.048 * [.019; .079]	37.5	.030 * [.005; .065]	.025 * [.007; .041]	.055 * [.027; .086]	45.5
Courses Out. School												
<i>Basic</i>	.046 * [.018; .073]	.047 * [.036; .057]	.093 * [.062; .120]	50.5	.018 * [-.007; .042]	.060 * [.047; .071]	.078 * [.051; .105]	76.9	.017 [-.006; .041]	.075 * [.060; .090]	.093 * [.062; .121]	80.7
<i>Achievement</i>	.035 * [.007; .062]	.023 * [.013; .032]	.058 * [.029; .088]	39.7	.016 [-.011; .041]	.034 * [.023; .046]	.050 * [.021; .079]	68.0	.015 [-.008; .039]	.043 * [.029; .056]	.058 * [.029; .085]	74.1
<i>Decisions</i>	.021 [-.006; .046]	.031 * [.021; .040]	.052 * [.023; .079]	59.6	.019 [-.007; .043]	.023 * [.011; .035]	.042 * [.014; .069]	54.8	.018 [-.006; .043]	.033 * [.019; .047]	.051 * [.022; .080]	64.7
<i>All</i>	.022 [-.005; .049]	.019 * [.009; .028]	.041 * [.012; .070]	46.3	.017 [-.009; .042]	.018 * [.007; .031]	.035 * [.007; .062]	52.9	.017 [-.007; .041]	.025 * [.011; .038]	.042 * [.013; .070]	59.5

Note: Confidence intervals were obtained using R = 1,500 bootstraps. N = 8,317. Missing values were imputed m = 10 times. The four covariate sets included the following variables. [1] “Basic”: parental income, parental occupation, parental education, parental highbrow activities, parental cultural possessions, students’ gender, immigrant background. [2] “Achievement”: Basic + mathematics and reading competencies from grade 5 (wave 1). [3] “Decisions”: Basic + aspirations and academic track from grade 5 (wave 1). [4] “All”: Basic + Achievement + Decisions

Figure A1: Summary of standardized mean differences and Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistics after balancing

Note: Summary of results from a total of 20 weighting procedures. The four covariate sets included the following variables. [1] “Basic”: parental income, parental occupation, parental education, parental highbrow activities, parental cultural possessions, students’ gender, immigrant background. [2] “Achievement”: Basic + mathematics and reading competencies from grade 5 (wave 1). [3] “Decisions”: Basic + aspirations and academic track from grade 5 (wave 1). [4] “All”: Basic + Achievement + Decisions

Figure A2: Average Treatment Effects using four different sets of covariates

Note: N = 8,317. Missing values were imputed m = 10 times. The four covariate sets included the following variables. [1] “Basic”: parental income, parental occupation, parental education, parental highbrow activities, parental cultural possessions, students’ gender, immigrant background. [2] “Achievement”: Basic + mathematics and reading competencies from grade 5 (wave 1). [3] “Decisions”: Basic + aspirations and academic track from grade 5 (wave 1). [4] “All”: Basic + Achievement + Decisions

Figure A3: Mediation Effects using four different sets of covariates

Note: Confidence intervals were obtained using R = 1,500 bootstraps. N = 8,317. Missing values were imputed m = 10 times. The four sets included the following covariates. [1] “Basic”: parental income, parental occupation, parental education, parental highbrow activities, parental cultural possessions, students’ gender, immigrant background. [2] “Achievement”: Basic + mathematics and reading competencies from grade 5 (wave 1). [3] “Decisions”: Basic + aspirations and academic track from grade 5 (wave 1). [4] “All”: Basic + Achievement + Decisions